

THE IMPORTANCE OF DOMESTIC BANKS' PRECIOUS METALS ACCOUNTING OPERATIONS

Dilrabo Malikova

Faculty of Banking and Financial Services, Samarkand Institute of Economics
and Service,

Samarkand, Uzbekistan

E-mail address: dilrabo7malikova@gmail.com

Ibodot Ochilova

Faculty of Accounting, Tax and Finance, Samarkand Branch of Tashkent State
University of Economics,

Samarkand, Uzbekistan

Abstract – *The paper deals with the deposit operations of commercial banks, types of deposits in Uzbekistan, the essence and role of impersonal metal accounts. Moreover, the article presents the importance of expanding the volume of operations of domestic commercial banks on impersonal metal accounts.*

Keywords – commercial bank, deposit operations, bank account, time deposits, savings deposits, certificates of deposit, savings certificates, gold bullion, impersonal metal accounts.

1. INTRODUCTION

The banking sector plays a key role in the socio-economic development of all countries. The banking system of the Republic of Uzbekistan is currently represented by 33 commercial banks that provide the traditional range of banking services - lending, deposit operations, settlement and cash services, etc.

Attracting additional resources to the banking system, primarily through

the further growth of deposits of legal entities and individuals in the national currency, as well as the entry of banks into international capital markets, is a priority task defined in the strategy for reforming the banking system of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2020-2025.

Nowadays to the transactions of commercial banks with precious metals are given very little importance, which in turn hinders the expansion of the deposit base of banks, and also leads to a lack of revenue from the non-use of this financial instrument. In this regard, the issues of introducing new and improving existing banking products and services, is an urgent topic.

2. THEORETICAL ASPECTS

Deposit operations are operations of banks to attract funds from legal entities and individuals into demand deposits or into deposits for a certain period.

The subjects of deposit operations are enterprises of all organizational and legal forms and individuals.

The objects of deposit operations are deposits, i.e. the amount of money that the subjects of deposit operations pay in to bank accounts.

The implementation of deposit operations requires the development by each credit institution of its own deposit policy, which should be as a set of activities of a commercial bank aimed at determining the forms, tasks, content of banking activities for the formation of banking resources, their planning and regulation.

The ultimate goal of developing and implementing an effective deposit policy of any commercial bank is to increase the volume of the resource base while minimizing the bank's expenses and maintaining the required level of liquidity with an allowance for all types of risks.

Deposits are the main type of resources attracted by commercial banks. Indeed, deposits disclose the content of the activities of a commercial bank as an

intermediary in acquiring resources in the free market of credit resources.

A deposit refers to deposited funds that meet all of the following conditions:

- funds that must be returned at the customer's request or after the deadline, with or without interest or other income, or on the basis of agreed terms between the depositor or its authorized representative and the bank receiving the funds;

- funds that are not subject to subordinated debt, ownership rights or services, including insurance services;

- funds confirmed in writing with the relevant document of the bank receiving the funds.

Based on the category of depositors, deposits are distinguished:

- deposits of legal entities (enterprises, organizations, other banks);
- deposits of individuals.

In accordance with the current legislative acts in commercial banks of Uzbekistan, potential customers can open demand deposits, time deposits, savings deposits and other deposit accounts.

One way to increase the volume of attracted resources is the variety of deposits for different segments of the population, depending on the social level, as well as the amount and term of deposit.

Increasing competition in the banking environment forces credit institutions to resort to the struggle for the depositor and to methods such as providing a full range of services related to servicing the estimate of a particular client.

In addition to the above deposits, in practice of domestic banks in Uzbekistan certificates are issued into circulation in two forms:

- a) "deposit certificates" - for legal entities;
- b) "savings certificates" - for individuals.

Certificates are usually issued for a period of 6 months to 3 years.

3. ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

Deposits are the source of the formation of the loan capital of the bank, which is used to issue loans, make investments, etc. These banking operations bring the bank revenue. Therefore, the bank pays the citizen his deposit. The interest on deposits to a citizen is a payment for the invested money.

In foreign practice, the part uses impersonal (anonymous) metal accounts opened by the bank to account for precious metals. For example, impersonal metal accounts are widely used in the US, in the EU, in the Russian Federation, and also in Kazakhstan since 2017, etc. Their profitability depends on the dynamics of prices for the metal in which the account is opened. You can open accounts in four types of metals: gold, silver, platinum and palladium. Usually opening an account and maintaining it for free. But when closing accounts, customers incur small expenses, as they receive the amount set by the bank based on the purchase price of a particular metal. The spread between the purchase price and the sale price for each bank is, as a rule, several percent. In this spread, in fact, the bank profits from the opening and maintenance of metal accounts.

The key advantage of impersonal metal accounts is that they allow the investor to avoid the risks and costs associated with the transportation and storage of bullions of precious metals. Since banks do not buy gold, they do not bear the costs associated with the purchase and storage of precious metal, which makes this tool cheaper.

However, it should be noted that the main problem preventing the introduction of a new banking product is the lack of a regulatory framework.

In 2021, Uzbekistan adopted a law “On precious metals and precious stones”, which is aimed in particular at creating conditions for the use of precious metals and precious stones as investments and a financial instrument of savings.

Moreover, this legal act proposes to allow savings to be stored in precious metals not only to legal entities, but also to individuals, including non-residents.

Today, gold is one of the most popular instruments for investment, where investors share for 30-40% of the total volume of gold purchases. However, strategically, the price and investment changes in the gold market are quite diverse, and the overall mood of investors in the financial markets has a very strong impact on the price dynamics. With worsening economic expectations, investors, hedging the risks, increase investments in gold, while at times of stability demand for jewelry increases. In addition, the central banks of the countries actively participate in the market in order to diversify the state gold and foreign exchange reserves. Thus, the gold and currency reserves of the Republic of Uzbekistan, as on August 1, 2018, amounted to 27.4 billion US dollars, 50.4% of which is monetary gold.

Let's consider the advantages of investing money in gold bullions:

- gold is always, in all countries is a value. It does not become cheaper, and in periods of crises, on the contrary, it rises in price;
- gold is valued all over the world, because this is a rare metal. Its reserves in the world are not very large.

The combination of these properties allowed gold to become a material that is so highly valued around the world. Gold will never depreciate, and this fact should be decisive for making a decision about investing in gold bullions.

The bullion of bank gold can become not only an advantageous option for investment. The advantage of investing in this precious metal before investing in securities - you get rid of the need to monitor stock quotes every day on the stock exchange. But this is the case if you invest seriously and for a long time.

Advantage over deposits - investing money in gold bullion will allow you to keep the accumulation from inflation and financial crises, and get income. But you need to keep in mind that buying a gold bullion will not give you a quick

income. The price of gold is constantly fluctuating, but not so much, as, for example, the exchange rates or the value of securities.

4. CONCLUSIONS

The introduction of banking services as an investment in gold will reduce the need of the population in cash currency and create additional opportunities for attracting free funds of the population. The opening of impersonal metal accounts is possible in two ways: by depositing money and by placing a certain bullion. But the most optimal option for the initial stage of introducing a new banking service is the launch of the program for opening impersonal metal accounts by depositing money. That is, it will be necessary to limit the ability to withdraw gold from the bank itself, but only to ensure its purchase and sale and storage on deposit. This practice shows the popularity of gold as an analogue of the savings deposit, not only in the world, but also in the CIS countries. The attractiveness of this banking service is the lack of payment for VAT, storage costs, collection of metal and its expertise. Taking into account, the fact that Uzbekistan is among the first ten states-producers of this precious metal, it seems expedient to give such an opportunity to our citizens.

In conclusion, it should be noted that the creation of a new commodity market, stimulating the development of the financial market and corresponding production capacities, will help expand the opportunities of the stock market as an alternative source of attracting capital and placing free resources of enterprises, financial institutions and the population.

5. REFERENCES

- [1] Malikova, Dilrabo. "Deposit base of Uzbekistan commercial banks." World Scientific News 143 (2020): 115-126.

- [2] Agnieszka Butor-Keler, Customer Experience in the Banking Services Market, *World Scientific News* 134 (2) (2019), 148-160.
- [3] Tadeusz Trębacz, FinTech as an innovative banking sector, *World Scientific News* 122 (2019), 83-95.
- [4] Маликова, Д. М., & Ниязов, З. Д. (2020). Пути Расширения Депозитной Базы Коммерческих Банков. In *Российская экономика: взгляд в будущее* (pp. 122-125).
- [5] Маликова, Дилрабо Муминовна. "Пути расширения спектра инновационных услуг в Узбекистане." *European science* 4 (53) (2020): 21-23.
- [6] Тогаев, Салим. "ТИЖОРАТ БАНКЛАРИНИНГ МОЛИЯВИЙ БАРҚАРОРЛИГИНИ ТАЪМИНЛАШ ЙЎЛЛАРИ." *Scienceweb academic papers collection* (2021).
- [7] Muminovna, Malikova Dilrabo. "MONETARY AGGREGATES AND FEATURES OF THEIR STRUCTURE IN THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN." "ONLINE-CONFERENCES" PLATFORM. 2021.
- [8] Тогаев, Салим. "Topical issues of providing the financial stability of commercial banks." *Scienceweb academic papers collection* (2021).
- [9] Malikova, Dilrabo. "Consulting services market of Uzbekistan." *World Scientific News* 145 (2020): 168-179.